

VILNIUS UNIVERSITY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In Lithuania, the *Labour Code*¹ (2016) and the *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men*² (last amended in 2017) are the key legislation regulating how universities and research organisations address the issues of gender-based violence (GBV) at work and in education. The amended *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men* obliges higher education and research institutions to ensure equal rights for women and men and to undertake measures to stop any sexual harassment and protect students and staff in these institutions (2017, Art. 5 para. 5).

Universities have developed policies on antidiscrimination, equal opportunities, and diversity and have integrated gender as a category on which grounds discrimination, harassment, and sexual harassment is prohibited. Prevention and protection against sexual harassment are often the only types of action which the specific policies have been adopted. Some universities developed these policies after the Conference of University Rectors adopted in 2020 the Guidelines for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Investigation of Its Incidences (hereinafter the Guidelines).³ All universities have integrated the Recommendations on the Approval, Embedding, and Monitoring of Academic Ethics Codes by Research and Higher Education Institutions⁴ (hereinafter the Recommendations) approved by the Ombudsperson for Academic Ethics and Procedures. The Recommendations do not specifically mention GBV in universities, but they refer to integrity, justice, trust, equality, and responsibility as the main principles of academic ethics.

According to data from 2021, there are 11 public and four private universities in Lithuania. Six public and one private university have adopted policy documents on equal opportunities including gender equality and four public universities have adopted Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).

¹ Labour Code, No. XII-260 (2016, last amended 2021). <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/f6d686707e7011e6b969d7ae07280e89>.

² Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men, No. XII-2767 (2016, last amended 2017). <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/d6ed8e50a74a11e68987e8320e9a5185>.

³ The Conference of Universities' Rectors (2020). Guidelines for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Investigation of Its Incidence. https://lurk.lt/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Seksualinio-priekabiavimo-prevencijos-ir-atvej%C5%B3-nagrin%C4%97jimo-gair%C4%97s-2020m-be-nuorod%C5%B3_T.pdf.

⁴ Rekomendacijos mokslo ir studijų institucijų akademinės etikos kodeksų priėmimo, įgyvendinimo ir priežiūros rekomendacijos, V-16, (2015, last amendment 2020, V-38). <https://etikostarnyba.lt/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/V-38.pdf>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

Vilnius University adopted the Diversity and Equal Opportunities Strategy 2020–2025 (hereafter the Strategy) and its Implementation Plan for the Period 2020-2022. **The aim of the Strategy** is to create a study and work environment at the university that promotes individual, social, and cultural diversity and ensures equal opportunities for members of the university community. GBV is not directly addressed in the document, however, it addresses anti-discrimination measures to reduce direct and indirect discrimination as enshrined in the legislation of the Republic of Lithuania. This means that any discrimination, sexual harassment, or harassment in work relations on any grounds is prohibited. In addition, the Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men obliges educational and research establishments to take measures to prevent the sexual harassment of students and employees. Thus, issues relating to prevention and protection against sexual harassment and harassment at Vilnius University are integrated into the framework of its antidiscrimination policies.

The Code of Ethics of Vilnius University, a more general document, also addresses GBV by mentioning that actions exhibiting features of harassment or intimidation or having other negative effects are prohibited. In addition, Art.11.1 prohibits 'intimate relationships between an academic staff member and a student with whom the staff member is connected through the course unit being taught'.

The main stakeholders at the institutional level are:

- The Community Development Department of the Central Administration is responsible for formulating the equal opportunities policy measures at Vilnius University.
- The equal opportunities coordinator is responsible for developing the university's anti-discrimination policies and practices, monitoring and analysing equality of opportunity in the context of study and work, advising prospective and current students and employees on equality and diversity issues, and organising and coordinating investigations into discrimination cases. In addition, the equal opportunities coordinator may, within his/her competence, initiate and coordinate changes to secure equal opportunities and increase diversity, and represent individuals from different discriminated groups within the university's community, etc.
- In the case of any violations of academic ethics academic staff and student shall approach the university's Central Academic Ethics Commission.

URLs

- › The Strategy and Its Implementation Plan: <https://www.vu.lt/en/about-vu/equal-opportunities#strategy-for-the-period-of-2020-2025>; <https://www.vu.lt/en/about-vu/equal-opportunities#implementation-plan-for-the-period-of-2020-2022>
- › Code of Ethics: <https://www.vu.lt/apiemus/dokumentai#akademine-etika>
Document in English is available at:
https://www.vu.lt/site_files/Studies/Study_regulations/Code_of_academic_ethics_VU.pdf

Entry into force: The Policy entered into force in **2020** and the *Code of Ethics* in **2018**.

TRAINING

An e-training programme on recognising and preventing sexual harassment was recently initiated.⁵ The course is strongly recommended for all members of the university community and especially newcomers. It is expected that this course will become mandatory for all newcomers including both students and staff.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

None.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies combined refer indirectly to **two** forms of GBV, which are sexual harassment and harassment, as forms of discrimination enshrined in the *Labour Code*, the *Act on Equal Opportunities*, and the *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men*.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The two policies combined address the following **2Ps**: prevalence and prevention. The Code of Ethics is the only policy that explicitly addresses the Ps. The Strategy in itself does not cover any P but its Implementation Plan addresses prevention and the provision of services.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

⁵ Vilnius University (7 April 2021). Nauja e. mokymų programa VU bendruomenei „Seksualinio priekabiavimo atpažinimas ir prevencija“ Vilnius University. Retrieved from <https://naujienos.vu.lt/nauja-e-mokymu-programa-vu-bendruomenei-seksualinio-priekabiavimo-atpažinimas-ir-prevencija/>.

Target groups: Both documents address academic and non-academic staff and students.

Specific vulnerable groups: Both policy documents address **seven** groups as particularly vulnerable to GBV: international students and staff, staff and students with disabilities, students with socially complex backgrounds, and staff and students who have children.

Intersectionality addressed: No.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. The Strategy includes the general data monitoring instrument of quantitative surveys and qualitative research to measure the prevalence of discrimination and the grounds of discrimination and to provide an impact assessment, but it does not provide further detail.

Evaluation: Yes. There is an impact assessment of the implementation of the Strategy and its Implementation Plan, which takes the form of an annual report that is submitted to the Senate for approval.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

None of the policies set out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigation. However, there is one mechanism in place.

The Trustline⁶ was established in 2018 and it makes it possible for any member of the university community who has experienced sexual harassment or discrimination to file a complaint, get assistance, and expect fair investigation and proper outcomes from the investigation.

Who to contact: The equal opportunities coordinator by e-mail; the e-mail is posted on the university's website <https://www.vu.lt/en/about-vu/equal-opportunities> (English version) and <https://www.vu.lt/apiemus/lygios-galimybes> (Lithuanian version).

Investigation procedure: Investigations are conducted by a dedicated team (made up of professional psychologists and lawyers) that promptly examines a complaint and provides

⁶ <https://www.vu.lt/en/about-vu/equal-opportunities>

assistance while guaranteeing complete confidentiality. Each case is treated individually. The equal opportunities coordinator performs the role of a mediator in organising the process to address a violation reported by a complainant. Upon receiving a complaint, the equal opportunities coordinator ascertains the complainant's preferences on whether to disclose the issue publicly or keep it anonymised without disclosing personal names. In both cases protection of the complainant is ensured. The equal opportunities coordinator approaches the persons at the faculty in positions of responsibility and sets up a team to address the issue.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

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